

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
1	1	Bubblesort-LSC-N	Canton	Same	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE

```

1 public static int[] bubbleSort(int[] a) {
2     boolean swapped;
3     int n = a.length - 2;
4
5     do {
6         swapped = false;
7         for (int i = 0; i <= n; i++) {
8             if (a[i] > a[i + 1]) {
9                 int tmp = a[i];
10                a[i] = a[i + 1];
11                a[i + 1] = tmp;
12                swapped = true;
13            }
14        }
15        n = n - 1;
16    } while (swapped);
17
18    return a;
19 }

```

```

1 public static int[] bubbleSort(int[] numbers) {
2     boolean swapped = false;
3
4     do {
5         swapped = false;
6         for (int i = 0; i < (numbers.length - 1); ++i) {
7             if (numbers[i] > numbers[i + 1]) {
8                 int temp = numbers[i];
9                 numbers[i] = numbers[i+1];
10                numbers[i+1] = temp;
11                swapped = true;
12            }
13        }
14    } while (swapped);
15
16    return numbers;
17 }

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	49	Bubblesort-LSC-x	Canton	Same	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static int[] ANON(int[] a) { 2 boolean s; 3 int n = a.length - 2; 4 5 do { 6 s = false; 7 for (int i = 0; i <= n; i++) { 8 if (a[i] > a[i + 1]) { 9 int tmp = a[i]; 10 a[i] = a[i + 1]; 11 a[i + 1] = tmp; 12 s = true; 13 } 14 } 15 n = n - 1; 16 } while (s); 17 18 return a; 19 } </pre> <pre> 1 public static int[] ANON(int[] n) { 2 boolean s = false; 3 4 do { 5 s = false; 6 7 for (int i = 0; i < n.length - 1; ++i) { 8 if (n[i] > n[i + 1]) { 9 int temp = n[i]; 10 n[i] = n[i+1]; 11 n[i+1] = temp; 12 s = true; 13 } 14 } 15 } while (s); 16 17 return n; 18 } 19 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
1	50	Bubblesort-LS_x	Lombard	Same	Different	TRUE	Obfuscated	FALSE

```

1 public static int[] ANON(int[] a) {
2     boolean s;
3     int n = a.length - 2;
4
5     do {
6         s = false;
7         for (int i = 0; i <= n; i++) {
8             if (a[i] > a[i + 1]) {
9                 int tmp = a[i];
10                a[i] = a[i + 1];
11                a[i + 1] = tmp;
12                s = true;
13            }
14        }
15        n = n - 1;
16    } while (s);
17
18    return a;
19 }

```

```

1 public static int[] ANON(int[] a) {
2     boolean s = true;
3     for(int i = a.length - 1; i > 0 && s; i--) {
4         s = false;
5         for(int j = 0; j < i; j++) {
6             if(a[j+1] > a[j]) {
7                 int t = a[j];
8                 a[j] = a[j + 1];
9                 a[j + 1] = t;
10                s = true;
11            }
12        }
13    }
14    return a;
15 }
16
17
18
19 }

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	2	Bubblesort-LS_N	Lombard	Same	Different	TRUE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static int[] bubbleSort(int[] a) { 2 boolean swapped; 3 int n = a.length - 2; 4 5 do { 6 swapped = false; 7 for (int i = 0; i <= n; i++) { 8 if (a[i] > a[i + 1]) { 9 int tmp = a[i]; 10 a[i] = a[i + 1]; 11 a[i + 1] = tmp; 12 swapped = true; 13 } 14 } 15 n = n - 1; 16 } while (swapped); 17 18 return a; 19 } </pre> <pre> 1 public static int[] bubbleSort(int[] array) 2 { 3 boolean swapped = true; 4 for(int i = array.length - 1; i > 0 && swapped; i--) 5 { 6 swapped = false; 7 for(int j = 0; j < i; j++) 8 { 9 if(array[j+1] > array[j]) { 10 int tempInt = array[j]; 11 array[j] = array[j + 1]; 12 array[j + 1] = tempInt; 13 swapped = true; 14 } 15 } 16 } 17 return array; 18 } 19 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	3	Bubblesort-L_C-N	Beale	Same	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 def bubblesort(lst): 2 for i in range(len(lst)-1): 3 for j in range(len(lst)-1): 4 if (lst[j]>lst[j+1]): 5 t=lst[j] 6 lst[j]=lst[j+1] 7 lst[j+1]=t 8 return lst 9 10 </pre> <pre> 1 def bubbleSort(arr): 2 length = len(arr) - 1 3 swap = True 4 while swap: 5 swap = False 6 for i in range(length): 7 if arr[i + 1] < arr[i]: 8 arr[i], arr[i + 1] = arr[i + 1], arr[i] 9 swap = True 10 return arr </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	51	Bubblesort-L_C-x	Beale	Same	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 def ANON(lst): 2 for i in range(len(lst)-1): 3 for j in range(len(lst)-1): 4 if (lst[j]>lst[j+1]): 5 t=lst[j] 6 lst[j]=lst[j+1] 7 lst[j+1]=t 8 return lst 9 10 </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(arr): 2 l = len(arr) - 1 3 s = True 4 while s: 5 s = False 6 for i in range(l): 7 if arr[i + 1] < arr[i]: 8 arr[i], arr[i + 1] = arr[i + 1], arr[i] 9 s = True 10 return arr </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	52	Bubblesort-L__x	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 def ANON(nums): 2 for i in range(len(nums) - 1): 3 for j in range(len(nums) - i - 1): 4 if nums[j] > nums[j + 1]: 5 nums[j], nums[j + 1] = \ 6 nums[j + 1], nums[j] 7 return nums 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(u): 2 l = len(u) - 1 3 s = False 4 5 while not s: 6 s = True 7 for i in range(0, l): 8 if (u[i] < u[i+1]): 9 s = False 10 tmp = u[i] 11 u[i] = u[i+1] 12 u[i+1] = tmp 13 14 return u </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	4	Bubblesort-L__-N	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 def bubbleSort(nums): 2 for i in range(len(nums) - 1): 3 for j in range(len(nums) - i - 1): 4 if nums[j] > nums[j + 1]: 5 nums[j], nums[j + 1] = \ 6 nums[j + 1], nums[j] 7 return nums 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 </pre> <pre> 1 def bubbleSort(unsortedList): 2 length = len(unsortedList) - 1 3 isSorted = False 4 5 while not isSorted: 6 isSorted = True 7 for i in range(0, length): 8 if (unsortedList[i] < unsortedList[i+1]): 9 isSorted = False 10 temp = unsortedList[i] 11 unsortedList[i] = unsortedList[i+1] 12 unsortedList[i+1] = temp 13 14 return unsortedList </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
1	53	Bubblesort_SC-x	Wall	Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE

```

1 public static int[] ANON(int[] n) {
2     boolean s = false;
3
4     do {
5         s = false;
6
7         for (int i = 0; i < n.length - 1; ++i) {
8             if (n[i] > n[i + 1]) {
9                 int temp = n[i];
10                n[i] = n[i+1];
11                n[i+1] = temp;
12                s = true;
13            }
14        }
15    } while (s);
16
17    return n;
18 }
19
1 def ANON(arr):
2     l = len(arr) - 1
3     s = True
4     while s:
5         s = False
6         for i in range(l):
7             if arr[i + 1] < arr[i]:
8                 arr[i], arr[i + 1] = arr[i + 1], arr[i]
9                 s = True
10        return arr
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	5	Bubblesort_SC-N	Wall	Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static int[] bubbleSort(int[] numbers) { 2 boolean swapped = false; 3 4 do { 5 swapped = false; 6 7 for (int i = 0; i < (numbers.length - 1); ++i) { 8 if (numbers[i] > numbers[i + 1]) { 9 int temp = numbers[i]; 10 numbers[i] = numbers[i+1]; 11 numbers[i+1] = temp; 12 swapped = true; 13 } 14 } 15 } while (swapped); 16 17 return numbers; 18 } 19 </pre> <pre> 1 def bubbleSort(arr): 2 length = len(arr) - 1 3 swap = True 4 while swap: 5 swap = False 6 for i in range(length): 7 if arr[i + 1] < arr[i]: 8 arr[i], arr[i + 1] = arr[i + 1], arr[i] 9 swap = True 10 return arr 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	54	Bubblesort-_S_-x	Mulholland	Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static int[] ANON(int[] a) { 2 boolean s = true; 3 for(int i = a.length - 1; i > 0 && s; i--) { 4 s = false; 5 for(int j = 0; j < i; j++) { 6 if(a[j+1] > a[j]) { 7 int t = a[j]; 8 a[j] = a[j + 1]; 9 a[j + 1] = t; 10 s = true; 11 } 12 } 13 } 14 return a; 15 } </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(lst): 2 for i in range(len(lst)-1): 3 for j in range(len(lst)-1): 4 if (lst[j]>lst[j+1]): 5 t=lst[j] 6 lst[j]=lst[j+1] 7 lst[j+1]=t 8 return lst </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	6	Bubblesort-_S_-N	Mulholland	Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static int[] bubbleSort(int[] array) 2 { 3 boolean swapped = true; 4 for(int i = array.length - 1; i > 0 && swapped; i--) 5 { 6 swapped = false; 7 for(int j = 0; j < i; j++) 8 { 9 if(array[j+1] > array[j]) { 10 int tempInt = array[j]; 11 array[j] = array[j + 1]; 12 array[j + 1] = tempInt; 13 swapped = true; 14 } 15 } 16 } 17 return array; 18 } </pre> <pre> 1 def bubblesort(lst): 2 for i in range(len(lst)-1): 3 for j in range(len(lst)-1): 4 if (lst[j]>lst[j+1]): 5 t=lst[j] 6 lst[j]=lst[j+1] 7 lst[j+1]=t 8 return lst </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	55	Bubblesort_-_C-x	Sunset	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static int[] ANON(int[] n) { 2 boolean s = false; 3 4 do { 5 s = false; 6 7 for (int i = 0; i < n.length - 1; ++i) { 8 if (n[i] > n[i + 1]) { 9 int temp = n[i]; 10 n[i] = n[i+1]; 11 n[i+1] = temp; 12 s = true; 13 } 14 } 15 } while (s); 16 17 return n; 18 } 19 </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(nums): 2 for i in range(len(nums) - 1): 3 for j in range(len(nums) - i - 1): 4 if nums[j] > nums[j + 1]: 5 nums[j], nums[j + 1] = \ 6 nums[j + 1], nums[j] 7 return nums 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	7	Bubblesort__C-N	Sunset	Diferent	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static int[] bubbleSort(int[] numbers) { 2 boolean swapped = false; 3 4 do { 5 swapped = false; 6 7 for (int i = 0; i < (numbers.length - 1); ++i) { 8 if (numbers[i] > numbers[i + 1]) { 9 int temp = numbers[i]; 10 numbers[i] = numbers[i+1]; 11 numbers[i+1] = temp; 12 swapped = true; 13 } 14 } 15 16 } while (swapped); 17 18 return numbers; 19 } </pre> <pre> 1 def bubbleSort(nums): 2 for i in range(len(nums) - 1): 3 for j in range(len(nums) - i - 1): 4 if nums[j] > nums[j + 1]: 5 nums[j], nums[j + 1] = \ 6 nums[j + 1], nums[j] 7 return nums </pre>

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1	8	Bubblesort-__-N	Bourbon	Diferent	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static int[] bubbleSort(int[] vetor){ 2 int aux; 3 int temp; 4 5 for (int i = 0; i < vetor.length; i++) { 6 for (int j = 0; j < vetor.length - 1; j++) { 7 temp = j+1; 8 if (vetor[j] > vetor[temp]) { 9 aux = vetor[j]; 10 vetor[j] = vetor[temp]; 11 vetor[temp] = aux; 12 } 13 } 14 } 15 16 return vetor; 17 } </pre> <pre> 1 def bubbleSort(unsortedList): 2 length = len(unsortedList) - 1 3 isSorted = False 4 5 while not isSorted: 6 isSorted = True 7 for i in range(0, length): 8 if (unsortedList[i] < unsortedList[i+1]): 9 isSorted = False 10 temp = unsortedList[i] 11 unsortedList[i] = unsortedList[i+1] 12 unsortedList[i+1] = temp 13 14 return unsortedList 15 16 17 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
1	56	Bubblesort-__x	Bourbon	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static int[] ANON(int[] v){ 2 int aux; 3 int t; 4 5 for (int i = 0; i < v.length; i++) { 6 for (int j = 0; j < v.length - 1; j++) { 7 t = j+1; 8 if (v[j] > v[t]) { 9 aux = v[j]; 10 v[j] = v[t]; 11 v[t] = aux; 12 } 13 } 14 } 15 16 return v; 17 } </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(u): 2 l = len(u) - 1 3 s = False 4 5 while not s: 6 s = True 7 for i in range(0, l): 8 if (u[i] < u[i+1]): 9 s = False 10 tmp = u[i] 11 u[i] = u[i+1] 12 u[i+1] = tmp 13 14 return u 15 16 17 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	57	CamelCaser-LSC-x	Canton	Same	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 def ANON(s): 2 a = list(s) 3 for i in range(0, len(a)): 4 if i==0 or a[i-1]=='_': 5 a[i] = a[i].upper() 6 return ''.join(a.replace('_', '')) </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(s): 2 a = list(s) 3 for i in range(len(a)): 4 if i==0 or a[i-1]=='_': 5 a[i] = a[i].upper() 6 return ''.join([c for c in a if c != "_"]) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	9	CamelCaser-LSC-N	Canton	Same	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 def camel_case(string): 2 a = list(string) 3 for i in range(0, len(a)): 4 if i==0 or a[i-1]=='_': 5 a[i] = a[i].upper() 6 return ''.join(a).replace('_', '') </pre> <pre> 1 def camel_case(string): 2 a = list(string) 3 for i in range(len(a)): 4 if i==0 or a[i-1]=='_': 5 a[i] = a[i].upper() 6 return ''.join([c for c in a if c != "_"]) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
2	10	CamelCaser-LS_-N	Lombard	Same	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE

```

1 public static String camelCase(String str) {
2     if (str.length() == 0)
3         return "";
4
5     char[] strChr = str.toCharArray();
6     strChr[0] = Character.toUpperCase(strChr[0]);
7     for (int i = 0; i < strChr.length; i++) {
8         if (strChr[i] == '_' &&
9             i < strChr.length - 1) {
10            strChr[i + 1] = Character.toUpperCase(
11                strChr[i + 1]);
12        }
13    }
14    String reply = new String(strChr);
15    reply = reply.replace("_", "");
16    return reply;
17 }

```

```

1 public static String camelCaser(String str) {
2     if (str.length() == 0)
3         return "";
4
5     char[] strChr = str.toCharArray();
6     for (int i = 0; i < strChr.length; i++)
7         if (strChr[i] == '_')
8             strChr[i + 1] = Character.toUpperCase(strChr[i + 1]);
9     String reply = new String(strChr);
10    reply = reply.replace("_", "");
11    return reply;
12 }
13
14
15
16
17 }

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	58	CamelCaser-LS_-x	Lombard	Same	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String str) { 2 if (str.length() == 0) 3 return ""; 4 5 char[] s = str.toCharArray(); 6 s[0] = Character.toUpperCase(s[0]); 7 for (int i = 0; i < s.length; i++) { 8 if (s[i] == '_' && i < s.length - 1) { 9 s[i + 1] = Character.toUpperCase(s[i + 1]); 10 } 11 } 12 String r = new String(s); 13 r = r.replace("_", ""); 14 return r; 15 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	59	CamelCaser-L_C-x	Beale	Same	Same	TRUE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String str) { 2 String[] s = str.split("_"); 3 StringBuilder sb=new StringBuilder(); 4 for (String st : s) { 5 if (st.length(>0){ 6 sb.append(st.replaceFirst(7 st.substring(0, 1), 8 st.substring(0, 1).toUpperCase())); 9 } 10 } 11 } 12 return new String(sb); 13 } </pre> <pre> 1 public static String ANON(String str) { 2 String res = ""; 3 for (String w : str.split("_")) { 4 if (!w.isEmpty()) { 5 res += Character.toUpperCase(w.charAt(0)); 6 if (w.length() > 1) { 7 res += w.substring(1); 8 } 9 } 10 } 11 return res; 12 } 13 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
2	11	CamelCaser-L_C-N	Beale	Same	Same	TRUE	Meaningful	TRUE

```

1 public static String camelCase(String str) {
2     String[] strings = str.split("_");
3     StringBuilder stringBuilder=new StringBuilder();
4     for (String string : strings) {
5         if (string.length()>0){
6             stringBuilder.append(string.replaceFirst(
7                 string.substring(0, 1),
8                 string.substring(0, 1).toUpperCase()));
9         }
10    }
11 }
12 return new String(stringBuilder);
13 }

```

```

1 public static String camelCaser(String str) {
2     String res = "";
3     for (String word : str.split("_")) {
4         if (!word.isEmpty()) {
5             res += Character.toUpperCase(word.charAt(0));
6             if (word.length() > 1) {
7                 res += word.substring(1);
8             }
9         }
10    }
11    return res;
12 }
13 }

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	60	CamelCaser-L__x	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 def ANON(tx): 2 cap = True 3 ntx = '' 4 for t in tx: 5 if t == '_': 6 cap = True 7 continue 8 else: 9 if cap == True: 10 t = t.upper() 11 ntx = ntx + t 12 cap = False 13 return ntx </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(us): 2 s = us.split('_') 3 return s[0] + ''.join([s[0].upper() + s[1:] \ 4 for s in s[1:] if len(s) > 0]) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	12	CamelCaser-L__-N	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 def to_camel_case(text): 2 cap = True 3 newText = '' 4 for t in text: 5 if t == '_': 6 cap = True 7 continue 8 else: 9 if cap == True: 10 t = t.upper() 11 newText = newText + t 12 cap = False 13 return newText </pre> <pre> 1 def UnderscoreToCamelCase(under_score): 2 segments = under_score.split('_') 3 return segments[0] + ''.join([s[0].upper() + s[1:] \ 4 for s in segments[1:] if len(s) > 0]) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	13	CamelCaser_SC-N	Wall	Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String camelCase(String str) { 2 if (str.length() == 0) 3 return ""; 4 5 char[] strChr = str.toCharArray(); 6 strChr[0] = Character.toUpperCase(strChr[0]); 7 for (int i = 0; i < strChr.length; i++) { 8 if (strChr[i] == '_' && 9 i < strChr.length - 1) { 10 strChr[i + 1] = Character.toUpperCase(11 strChr[i + 1]); 12 } 13 } 14 String reply = new String(strChr); 15 reply = reply.replace("_", ""); 16 return reply; 17 } </pre> <pre> 1 def camel_case(string): 2 a = list(string) 3 for i in range(0, len(a)): 4 if i==0 or a[i-1]=='_': 5 a[i] = a[i].upper() 6 return ''.join(a).replace('_', '') </pre>

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2	61	CamelCaser-_SC-x	Wall	Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String str) { 2 if (str.length() == 0) 3 return ""; 4 5 char[] s = str.toCharArray(); 6 s[0] = Character.toUpperCase(s[0]); 7 for (int i = 0; i < s.length; i++) { 8 if (s[i] == '_' && i < s.length - 1) { 9 s[i + 1] = Character.toUpperCase(s[i + 1]); 10 } 11 } 12 String r = new String(s); 13 r = r.replace("_", ""); 14 return r; 15 } </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(s): 2 a = list(s) 3 for i in range(0, len(a)): 4 if i==0 or a[i-1]=='_': 5 a[i] = a[i].upper() 6 return ''.join(a).replace('_', '') </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	14	CamelCaser-_S_-N	Mulholland	Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String camelCase(String str) { 2 String[] strings = str.split("_"); 3 StringBuilder stringBuilder=new StringBuilder(); 4 for (String string : strings) { 5 if (string.length()>0){ 6 stringBuilder.append(string.replaceFirst(7 string.substring(0, 1), 8 string.substring(0, 1).toUpperCase())); 9 } 10 11 } 12 return new String(stringBuilder); 13 } </pre> <pre> 1 ~ def UnderscoreToCamelCase(under_score): 2 segments = under_score.split('_') 3 return segments[0] + ''.join([s[0].upper() + s[1:] \ 4 for s in segments[1:] if len(s) > 0]) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	62	CamelCaser-_S_-x	Mulholland	Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String str) { 2 String[] s = str.split("_"); 3 StringBuilder sb=new StringBuilder(); 4 for (String st : s) { 5 if (st.length()>0){ 6 sb.append(st.replaceFirst(7 st.substring(0, 1), 8 st.substring(0, 1).toUpperCase())); 9 } 10 } 11 return new String(sb); 12 } 13 </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(us): 2 s = us.split('_') 3 return s[0] + ''.join([s[0].upper() + s[1:] \ 4 for s in s[1:] if len(s) > 0]) 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	63	CamelCaser-__C-x	Sunset	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String str) { 2 String res = ""; 3 for (String w : str.split("_")) { 4 if (!w.isEmpty()) { 5 res += Character.toUpperCase(w.charAt(0)); 6 if (w.length() > 1) { 7 res += w.substring(1); 8 } 9 } 10 } 11 return res; 12 } </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(s): 2 a = list(s) 3 for i in range(len(a)): 4 if i==0 or a[i-1]=='_': 5 a[i] = a[i].upper() 6 return ''.join([c for c in a if c != "_"]) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	15	CamelCaser-__C-N	Sunset	Diferent	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String camelCaser(String str) { 2 String res = ""; 3 for (String word : str.split("_")) { 4 if (!word.isEmpty()) { 5 res += Character.toUpperCase(word.charAt(0)); 6 if (word.length() > 1) { 7 res += word.substring(1); 8 } 9 } 10 } 11 return res; 12 } </pre> <pre> 1 def camel_case(string): 2 a = list(string) 3 for i in range(len(a)): 4 if i==0 or a[i-1]=='_': 5 a[i] = a[i].upper() 6 return ''.join([c for c in a if c != "_"]) 7 8 9 10 11 12 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	64	CamelCaser-__-x	Bourbon	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String str) { 2 if (str.length() == 0) 3 return ""; 4 5 char[] s = str.toCharArray(); 6 s[0] = Character.toUpperCase(s[0]); 7 for (int i = 0; i < s.length; i++) { 8 if (s[i] == '_' && i < s.length - 1) { 9 s[i + 1] = Character.toUpperCase(s[i + 1]); 10 } 11 } 12 String r = new String(s); 13 r = r.replace("_", ""); 14 return r; 15 } </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(us): 2 s = us.split('_') 3 return s[0] + ''.join([s[0].upper() + s[1:] \ 4 for s in s[1:] if len(s) > 0]) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
2	16	CamelCaser-__-N	Bourbon	Different	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String camelCase(String str) { 2 if (str.length() == 0) 3 return ""; 4 5 char[] strChr = str.toCharArray(); 6 strChr[0] = Character.toUpperCase(strChr[0]); 7 for (int i = 0; i < strChr.length; i++) { 8 if (strChr[i] == '_' && 9 i < strChr.length - 1) { 10 strChr[i + 1] = Character.toUpperCase(11 strChr[i + 1]); 12 } 13 } 14 String reply = new String(strChr); 15 reply = reply.replace("_", ""); 16 return reply; 17 } </pre> <pre> 1 def UnderscoreToCamelCase(under_score): 2 segments = under_score.split('_') 3 return segments[0] + ''.join([s[0].upper() + s[1:] \ 4 for s in segments[1:] if len(s) > 0]) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	65	Interleave-LSC-x	Canton	Same	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 def ANON(a, b): 2 arg = [a, b] 3 ml = max([len(i) for i in arg]) 4 r = [] 5 6 for j in range(ml): 7 for k in arg: 8 try: 9 r.append(k[j]) 10 except: 11 pass 12 13 return "".join(r) </pre>

```

1  def ANON(a, b):
2      arg = [a,b]
3      r = []
4      m = max(map(len, arg))
5      for i in range(m):
6          for arr in arg:
7              try:
8                  r.append(arr[i])
9              except:
10                 pass
11             return "".join(r)
12
13

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	17	Interleave-LSC-N	Canton	Same	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 def interleave(a, b): 2 args = [a, b] 3 max_length = max([len(i) for i in args]) 4 r = [] 5 6 for j in range(max_length): 7 for k in args: 8 try: 9 r.append(k[j]) 10 except: 11 pass 12 13 return "".join(r) </pre>
									<pre> 1 def interleave(a, b): 2 args = [a,b] 3 result = [] 4 m = max(map(len, args)) 5 for i in range(m): 6 for arr in args: 7 try: 8 result.append(arr[i]) 9 except: 10 pass 11 return "".join(result) 12 13 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	66	Interleave-LS_x	Lombard	Same	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 def ANON(a, b): 2 arg = [a,b] 3 r = [] 4 m = max(map(len, arg)) 5 for i in range(m): 6 for arr in arg: 7 try: 8 r.append(arr[i]) 9 except: 10 pass 11 return "".join(r) </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(s1, s2): 2 arg = [s1, s2] 3 arr = "" 4 for i in range(min(len(a) for a in arg)): 5 for j in range(len(arg)): 6 try: arr += arg[j][i] 7 except: pass 8 return arr </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	18	Interleave-LS_N	Lombard	Same	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 def interleave(a, b): 2 args = [a,b] 3 result = [] 4 m = max(map(len, args)) 5 for i in range(m): 6 for arr in args: 7 try: 8 result.append(arr[i]) 9 except: 10 pass 11 return "".join(result) </pre>
									<pre> 1 def interleave(s1, s2): 2 args = [s1, s2] 3 arr = "" 4 for i in range(min(len(a) for a in args)): 5 for j in range(len(args)): 6 try: arr += args[j][i] 7 except: pass 8 return arr </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	19	Interleave-L_C-N	Beale	Same	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String interleave(String you, 2 String me) { 3 StringBuilder result = new StringBuilder(); 4 for (int i = 0; 5 i < Math.max(you.length(), me.length()); 6 i++) { 7 if (i < you.length()) { 8 result.append(you.charAt(i)); 9 } 10 if (i < me.length()) { 11 result.append(me.charAt(i)); 12 } 13 } 14 return result.toString(); 15 } 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24 </pre>
									<pre> 1 public static String interleave(String a, 2 String b) { 3 char[][] arrays = new char[][] 4 {a.toCharArray(), b.toCharArray()}; 5 6 int len = 0; 7 for (char[] ar : arrays) { 8 len += ar.length; 9 } 10 char[] res = new char[len]; 11 12 int level = 0, i = 0; 13 while (i < len) { 14 for (char[] ar : arrays) { 15 if (level < ar.length) { 16 res[i] = ar[level]; 17 i++; 18 } 19 } 20 level++; 21 } 22 23 return new String(res); 24 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	67	Interleave-L_C-x	Beale	Same	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String you, 2 String me) { 3 StringBuilder r = new StringBuilder(); 4 for (int i = 0; 5 i < Math.max(you.length(), me.length()); 6 i++) { 7 if (i < you.length()) { 8 r.append(you.charAt(i)); 9 } 10 if (i < me.length()) { 11 r.append(me.charAt(i)); 12 } 13 } 14 return r.toString(); 15 } 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24 </pre> <pre> 1 public static String ANON(String a, 2 String b) { 3 char[][] ars = new char[][] 4 {a.toCharArray(), b.toCharArray()}; 5 6 int len = 0; 7 for (char[] ar : ars) { 8 len += ar.length; 9 } 10 char[] res = new char[len]; 11 12 int l = 0, i = 0; 13 while (i < len) { 14 for (char[] ar : ars) { 15 if (l < ar.length) { 16 res[i] = ar[l]; 17 i++; 18 } 19 } 20 l++; 21 } 22 23 return new String(res); 24 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	68	Interleave-L__-x	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String a, 2 String b) { 3 char[][] ars = new char[][] 4 {a.toCharArray(), b.toCharArray()}; 5 6 int len = 0; 7 for (char[] ar : ars) { 8 len += ar.length; 9 } 10 char[] res = new char[len]; 11 12 int l = 0, i = 0; 13 while (i < len) { 14 for (char[] ar : ars) { 15 if (l < ar.length) { 16 res[i] = ar[l]; 17 i++; 18 } 19 } 20 l++; 21 } 22 23 return new String(res); 24 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	20	Interleave-L__-N	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String interleave(String a, 2 String b) { 3 char[][] arrays = new char[][] 4 {a.toCharArray(), b.toCharArray()}; 5 6 int len = 0; 7 for (char[] ar : arrays) { 8 len += ar.length; 9 } 10 char[] res = new char[len]; 11 12 int level = 0, i = 0; 13 while (i < len) { 14 for (char[] ar : arrays) { 15 if (level < ar.length) { 16 res[i] = ar[level]; 17 i++; 18 } 19 } 20 level++; 21 } 22 23 return new String(res); 24 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
3	69	Interleave_SC-x	Wall	Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE

```

1 public static String ANON(String you,
2     String me) {
3     StringBuilder r = new StringBuilder();
4     for (int i = 0;
5         i < Math.max(you.length(), me.length());
6         i++) {
7         if (i < you.length()) {
8             r.append(you.charAt(i));
9         }
10        if (i < me.length()) {
11            r.append(me.charAt(i));
12        }
13    }
14    return r.toString();
15 }

```

```

1 def ANON(one, two):
2     l1, l2 = len(one), len(two)
3     s = []
4     for i in range(max(l1, l2)):
5         if i < l1: s.append(one[i])
6         if i < l2: s.append(two[i])
7     return "".join(s)
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
3	21	Interleave_SC-N	Wall	Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE

```

1 public static String interleave(String you,
2                               String me) {
3     StringBuilder result = new StringBuilder();
4     for (int i = 0;
5         i < Math.max(you.length(), me.length());
6         i++) {
7         if (i < you.length()) {
8             result.append(you.charAt(i));
9         }
10        if (i < me.length()) {
11            result.append(me.charAt(i));
12        }
13    }
14    return result.toString();
15 }

```

```

1 def interleave(one, two):
2     l1, l2 = len(one), len(two)
3     s = []
4     for i in range(max(l1, l2)):
5         if i < l1: s.append(one[i])
6         if i < l2: s.append(two[i])
7     return "".join(s)
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	22	Interleave_S_N	Mulholland	Diferent	Different	TRUE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String interleave(String a, 2 String b) { 3 char[][] arrays = new char[][] 4 {a.toCharArray(), b.toCharArray()}; 5 6 int len = 0; 7 for (char[] ar : arrays) { 8 len += ar.length; 9 } 10 char[] res = new char[len]; 11 12 int level = 0, i = 0; 13 while (i < len) { 14 for (char[] ar : arrays) { 15 if (level < ar.length) { 16 res[i] = ar[level]; 17 i++; 18 } 19 } 20 level++; 21 } 22 23 return new String(res); 24 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	70	Interleave_S_x	Mulholland	Diferent	Different	TRUE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String a, 2 String b) { 3 char[][] ars = new char[][] 4 {a.toCharArray(), b.toCharArray()}; 5 6 int len = 0; 7 for (char[] ar : ars) { 8 len += ar.length; 9 } 10 char[] res = new char[len]; 11 12 int l = 0, i = 0; 13 while (i < len) { 14 for (char[] ar : ars) { 15 if (l < ar.length) { 16 res[i] = ar[l]; 17 i++; 18 } 19 } 20 l++; 21 } 22 23 return new String(res); 24 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	23	Interleave-__C-N	Sunset	Diferent	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String interleave(String you, 2 String me) { 3 char[] a = you.toCharArray(); 4 char[] b = me.toCharArray(); 5 StringBuilder out = new StringBuilder(); 6 int maxLength = Math.max(a.length, b.length); 7 for (int i = 0; i < maxLength; i++) { 8 if (i < a.length) out.append(a[i]); 9 if (i < b.length) out.append(b[i]); 10 } 11 return out.toString(); 12 } 13 1 def interleave(a, b): 2 args = [a, b] 3 max_length = max([len(i) for i in args]) 4 r = [] 5 6 for j in range(max_length): 7 for k in args: 8 try: 9 r.append(k[j]) 10 except: 11 pass 12 13 return "".join(r) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	71	Interleave-__C-x	Sunset	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String you, 2 String me) { 3 char[] a = you.toCharArray(); 4 char[] b = me.toCharArray(); 5 StringBuilder out = new StringBuilder(); 6 int m = Math.max(a.length, b.length); 7 for (int i = 0; i < m; i++) { 8 if (i < a.length) out.append(a[i]); 9 if (i < b.length) out.append(b[i]); 10 } 11 return out.toString(); 12 } 13 1 def ANON(a, b): 2 arg = [a, b] 3 ml = max([len(i) for i in arg]) 4 r = [] 5 6 for j in range(ml): 7 for k in arg: 8 try: 9 r.append(k[j]) 10 except: 11 pass 12 13 return "".join(r) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	24	Interleave-___-N	Bourbon	Different	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String interleave(String letters1, 2 String letters2){ 3 ArrayList<Character> combinedChars = 4 new ArrayList<>(); 5 6 for (int i = 0; i < letters1.length(); i++){ 7 combinedChars.add(letters1.charAt(i)); 8 combinedChars.add(letters2.charAt(i)); 9 } 10 11 return String.valueOf(combinedChars.toArray()); 12 } </pre> <pre> 1 def interleave(a, b): 2 args = [a,b] 3 result = [] 4 m = max(map(len, args)) 5 for i in range(m): 6 for arr in args: 7 try: 8 result.append(arr[i]) 9 except: 10 pass 11 return "".join(result) 12 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
3	72	Interleave-__-x	Bourbon	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String l1, 2 String l2){ 3 ArrayList<Character> c = 4 new ArrayList<>(); 5 6 for (int i = 0; i < l1.length(); i++){ 7 c.add(l1.charAt(i)); 8 c.add(l2.charAt(i)); 9 } 10 11 return String.valueOf(c.toArray()); 12 } </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(a, b): 2 arg = [a,b] 3 r = [] 4 m = max(map(len, arg)) 5 for i in range(m): 6 for arr in arg: 7 try: 8 r.append(arr[i]) 9 except: 10 pass 11 return "".join(r) 12 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
4	73	Anagram-LSC-x	Canton	Same	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE

```

1 public static boolean ANON(String s1,
2     String s2) {
3     if (s1.length() != s2.length()) {
4         return false;
5     }
6     int[] c = new int[256];
7     for (int i = 0; i < s1.length(); i++) {
8         c[s1.charAt(i)]++;
9         c[s2.charAt(i)]--;
10    }
11    for (int i = 0; i < c.length; i++) {
12        if (c[i] != 0) {
13            return false;
14        }
15    }
16    return true;
17 }

```

```

1 public static boolean ANON(String s1,
2     String s2) {
3     if (s1.length() != s2.length())
4         return false;
5
6     int[] c1 = new int[256];
7     int[] c2 = new int[256];
8
9     for (int i = 0; i < s1.length(); i++) {
10        ++c1[s1.charAt(i)];
11        ++c2[s2.charAt(i)];
12    }
13
14    for (int i = 0; i < 256; i++)
15        if (c1[i] != c2[i])
16            return false;
17
18    return true;
19 }

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	25	Anagram-LSC-N	Canton	Same	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean isPermutation(String s1, 2 String s2) { 3 if (s1.length() != s2.length()) { 4 return false; 5 } 6 int[] charCount = new int[256]; 7 for (int i = 0; i < s1.length(); i++) { 8 charCount[s1.charAt(i)]++; 9 charCount[s2.charAt(i)]--; 10 } 11 for (int i = 0; i < charCount.length; i++) { 12 if (charCount[i] != 0) { 13 return false; 14 } 15 } 16 return true; 17 } 18 19 </pre> <pre> 1 public static boolean isAnagram(String str1, 2 String str2) { 3 if (str1.length() != str2.length()) 4 return false; 5 6 int[] count1 = new int[256]; 7 int[] count2 = new int[256]; 8 9 for (int i = 0; i < str1.length(); i++) { 10 ++count1[str1.charAt(i)]; 11 ++count2[str2.charAt(i)]; 12 } 13 14 for (int i = 0; i < 256; i++) 15 if (count1[i] != count2[i]) 16 return false; 17 18 return true; 19 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	26	Anagram-LS_-N	Lombard	Same	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 def isAnagram(s, t): 2 hash1 = {} 3 hash2 = {} 4 5 for char in s: 6 hash1[char] = hash1.get(char, 0) + 1 7 for char in t: 8 hash2[char] = hash2.get(char, 0) + 1 9 10 return hash1 == hash2 </pre> <pre> 1 def isAnagram(s, t): 2 m = {} 3 for c in s: 4 m[c] = m.get(c, 0) + 1 5 for c in t: 6 if c not in m or m[c] == 0: 7 return False 8 else: 9 m[c] -= 1 10 return True </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	74	Anagram-LS_x	Lombard	Same	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 def ANON(s, t): 2 h1 = {} 3 h2 = {} 4 5 for char in s: 6 h1[char] = h1.get(char, 0) + 1 7 for char in t: 8 h2[char] = h2.get(char, 0) + 1 9 10 return h1 == h2 </pre>
									<pre> 1 def ANON(s, t): 2 m = {} 3 for c in s: 4 m[c] = m.get(c, 0) + 1 5 for c in t: 6 if c not in m or m[c] == 0: 7 return False 8 else: 9 m[c] -= 1 10 return True </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	27	Anagram-L_C-N	Beale	Same	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 def isAnagram(s, t): 2 sLen = len(s) 3 tLen = len(t) 4 if sLen != tLen: 5 return False 6 s = sorted(s) 7 t = sorted(t) 8 for i in range(sLen): 9 if s[i] != t[i]: 10 return False 11 return True </pre>

```

1  def isAnagram(s, t):
2      hash1 = [0]*256
3      hash2 = [0]*256
4
5  for char in s:
6      hash1[ord(char)] += 1
7  for char in t:
8      hash2[ord(char)] += 1
9
10     return hash1 == hash2
11

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	75	Anagram-L_C-x	Beale	Same	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 def ANON(s, t): 2 ls = len(s) 3 lt = len(t) 4 if ls != lt: 5 return False 6 s = sorted(s) 7 t = sorted(t) 8 for i in range(ls): 9 if s[i] != t[i]: 10 return False 11 return True </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(s, t): 2 h1 = [0]*256 3 h2 = [0]*256 4 5 for char in s: 6 h1[ord(char)] += 1 7 for char in t: 8 h2[ord(char)] += 1 9 10 return h1 == h2 11 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	76	Anagram-L__x	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String s1, 2 String s2) { 3 char[] arr1 = s1.toCharArray(); 4 char[] arr2 = s2.toCharArray(); 5 6 java.util.Arrays.sort(arr1); 7 java.util.Arrays.sort(arr2); 8 9 s1 = new String(arr1); 10 s2 = new String(arr2); 11 12 return s1.equals(s2); 13 } 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 </pre> <pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String s1, 2 String s2) { 3 if (s1.length() != s2.length()) 4 return false; 5 s1 = s1.toLowerCase(); 6 s2 = s2.toLowerCase(); 7 8 int[] l = new int[1<<8]; 9 for (char c : s1.toCharArray()) { 10 l[c]++; 11 } 12 for (char c : s2.toCharArray()) { 13 l[c]--; 14 } 15 16 for (int i : l) { 17 if (i != 0) return false; 18 } 19 return true; 20 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	28	Anagram-L__N	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static boolean isAnagramSort(String str1, 2 String str2) { 3 char[] arr1 = str1.toCharArray(); 4 char[] arr2 = str2.toCharArray(); 5 6 java.util.Arrays.sort(arr1); 7 java.util.Arrays.sort(arr2); 8 9 str1 = new String(arr1); 10 str2 = new String(arr2); 11 12 return str1.equals(str2); 13 } 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 </pre> <pre> 1 public static boolean isAnagram(String s1, 2 String s2) { 3 if (s1.length() != s2.length()) 4 return false; 5 s1 = s1.toLowerCase(); 6 s2 = s2.toLowerCase(); 7 8 int[] letters = new int[1<<8]; 9 for (char c : s1.toCharArray()) { 10 letters[c]++; 11 } 12 for (char c : s2.toCharArray()) { 13 letters[c]--; 14 } 15 16 for (int i : letters) { 17 if (i != 0) return false; 18 } 19 return true; 20 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	29	Anagram_SC-N	Wall	Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean isAnagram(String str1, 2 String str2) { 3 if (str1.length() != str2.length()) 4 return false; 5 6 int[] count1 = new int[256]; 7 int[] count2 = new int[256]; 8 9 for (int i = 0; i < str1.length(); i++) { 10 ++count1[str1.charAt(i)]; 11 ++count2[str2.charAt(i)]; 12 } 13 14 for (int i = 0; i < 256; i++) 15 if (count1[i] != count2[i]) 16 return false; 17 18 return true; 19 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	77	Anagram_SC-x	Wall	Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String s1, 2 String s2) { 3 if (s1.length() != s2.length()) 4 return false; 5 6 int[] c1 = new int[256]; 7 int[] c2 = new int[256]; 8 9 for (int i = 0; i < s1.length(); i++) { 10 ++c1[s1.charAt(i)]; 11 ++c2[s2.charAt(i)]; 12 } 13 14 for (int i = 0; i < 256; i++) 15 if (c1[i] != c2[i]) 16 return false; 17 18 return true; 19 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	30	Anagram-_S_-N	Mulholland	Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static boolean isPermutation(String s1, 2 String s2) { 3 if (s1.length() != s2.length()) { 4 return false; 5 } 6 int[] charCount = new int[256]; 7 for (int i = 0; i < s1.length(); i++) { 8 charCount[s1.charAt(i)]++; 9 charCount[s2.charAt(i)]--; 10 } 11 for (int i = 0; i < charCount.length; i++) { 12 if (charCount[i] != 0) { 13 return false; 14 } 15 } 16 return true; 17 } </pre> <pre> 1 def isAnagram(s, t): 2 m = {} 3 for c in s: 4 m[c] = m.get(c, 0) + 1 5 for c in t: 6 if c not in m or m[c] == 0: 7 return False 8 else: 9 m[c] -= 1 10 return True </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
4	78	Anagram-_S_-x	Mulholland	Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE

```

1 public static boolean ANON(String s1,
2                             String s2) {
3     if (s1.length() != s2.length()) {
4         return false;
5     }
6     int[] c = new int[256];
7     for (int i = 0; i < s1.length(); i++) {
8         c[s1.charAt(i)]++;
9         c[s2.charAt(i)]--;
10    }
11    for (int i = 0; i < c.length; i++) {
12        if (c[i] != 0) {
13            return false;
14        }
15    }
16    return true;
17 }

```

```

1 def ANON(s, t):
2     m = {}
3     for c in s:
4         m[c] = m.get(c, 0) + 1
5     for c in t:
6         if c not in m or m[c] == 0:
7             return False
8     else:
9         m[c] -= 1
10    return True

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	31	Anagram_-_C-N	Sunset	Different	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean isAnagram(String str1, 2 String str2) { 3 if (str1.length() != str2.length()) 4 return false; 5 6 int[] count1 = new int[256]; 7 int[] count2 = new int[256]; 8 9 for (int i = 0; i < str1.length(); i++) { 10 ++count1[str1.charAt(i)]; 11 ++count2[str2.charAt(i)]; 12 } 13 14 for (int i = 0; i < 256; i++) 15 if (count1[i] != count2[i]) 16 return false; 17 18 return true; 19 } </pre>
									<pre> 1 def isAnagram(s, t): 2 slen = len(s) 3 tlen = len(t) 4 if slen != tlen: 5 return False 6 s = sorted(s) 7 t = sorted(t) 8 for i in range(slen): 9 if s[i] != t[i]: 10 return False 11 return True </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	79	Anagram-__C-x	Sunset	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String s1, 2 String s2) { 3 if (s1.length() != s2.length()) 4 return false; 5 6 int[] c1 = new int[256]; 7 int[] c2 = new int[256]; 8 9 for (int i = 0; i < s1.length(); i++) { 10 ++c1[s1.charAt(i)]; 11 ++c2[s2.charAt(i)]; 12 } 13 14 for (int i = 0; i < 256; i++) 15 if (c1[i] != c2[i]) 16 return false; 17 18 return true; 19 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	32	Anagram-__-N	Bourbon	Different	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static boolean isAnagram(String s1, 2 String s2) { 3 if (s1.length() != s2.length()) 4 return false; 5 s1 = s1.toLowerCase(); 6 s2 = s2.toLowerCase(); 7 8 int[] letters = new int[1<<8]; 9 for (char c : s1.toCharArray()) { 10 letters[c]++; 11 } 12 for (char c : s2.toCharArray()) { 13 letters[c]--; 14 } 15 16 for (int i : letters) { 17 if (i != 0) return false; 18 } 19 return true; 20 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
4	80	Anagram-__-x	Bourbon	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String s1, 2 String s2) { 3 if (s1.length() != s2.length()) 4 return false; 5 s1 = s1.toLowerCase(); 6 s2 = s2.toLowerCase(); 7 8 int[] l = new int[1<<8]; 9 for (char c : s1.toCharArray()) { 10 l[c]++; 11 } 12 for (char c : s2.toCharArray()) { 13 l[c]--; 14 } 15 16 for (int i : l) { 17 if (i != 0) return false; 18 } 19 return true; 20 } </pre>
									<pre> 1 def ANON(s, t): 2 ls = len(s) 3 lt = len(t) 4 if ls != lt: 5 return False 6 s = sorted(s) 7 t = sorted(t) 8 for i in range(ls): 9 if s[i] != t[i]: 10 return False 11 return True </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	81	Balanced-LSC-x	Canton	Same	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String b) { 2 Map<Character, Character> br = 3 new HashMap<>(); 4 br.put('(', ')'); 5 br.put('[', ']'); 6 br.put('{', '}'); 7 if (b.length() % 2 != 0) { 8 return false; 9 } 10 11 Stack<Character> h = new Stack(); 12 for (char ch : b.toCharArray()) { 13 if (br.containsKey(ch)) { 14 h.push(br.get(ch)); 15 } else if (h.isEmpty() 16 ch != h.pop()) { 17 return false; 18 } 19 } 20 return h.isEmpty(); 21 } </pre> <pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String s) { 2 HashMap<Character, Character> bm 3 = new HashMap<Character, Character>(); 4 bm.put('(', ')'); 5 bm.put('[', ']'); 6 bm.put('{', '}'); 7 Stack<Character> bs = new Stack<Character>(); 8 9 for (char c: s.toCharArray()) { 10 if (!bs.isEmpty() && 11 bm.get(bs.peek()) == c) { 12 bs.pop(); 13 } else if (bm.containsKey(c)) { 14 bs.push(c); 15 } else { 16 return false; 17 } 18 } 19 return bs.isEmpty(); 20 } 21 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	33	Balanced-LSC-N	Canton	Same	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean isBalanced(String brackets) { 2 Map<Character, Character> braces = 3 new HashMap<>(); 4 braces.put('(', ')'); 5 braces.put('[', ']'); 6 braces.put('{', '}'); 7 if (brackets.length() % 2 != 0) { 8 return false; 9 } 10 11 Stack<Character> halfBraces = new Stack(); 12 for (char ch : brackets.toCharArray()) { 13 if (braces.containsKey(ch)) { 14 halfBraces.push(braces.get(ch)); 15 } else if (halfBraces.isEmpty() 16 ch != halfBraces.pop()) { 17 return false; 18 } 19 } 20 return halfBraces.isEmpty(); 21 } </pre> <pre> 1 public static boolean isBalanced(String s) { 2 HashMap<Character, Character> bracketMap 3 = new HashMap<Character, Character>(); 4 bracketMap.put('{', '}'); 5 bracketMap.put('[', ']'); 6 bracketMap.put('(', ')'); 7 Stack<Character> bracketStack = 8 new Stack<Character>(); 9 10 for (char c: s.toCharArray()) { 11 if (!bracketStack.isEmpty() && 12 bracketMap.get(bracketStack.peek()) == c) { 13 bracketStack.pop(); 14 } else if (bracketMap.containsKey(c)) { 15 bracketStack.push(c); 16 } else { 17 return false; 18 } 19 } 20 return bracketStack.isEmpty(); 21 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	34	Balanced-LS_N	Lombard	Same	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 def isBalanced(strInput): 2 brackets = [('(',')'), ('[',']'), ('{','}')] 3 kStart = 0 4 kEnd = 1 5 stack = [] 6 7 for char in strInput: 8 for bracketPair in brackets: 9 if char == bracketPair[kStart]: 10 stack.append(char) 11 elif char == bracketPair[kEnd]: 12 if len(stack) == 0 or \ 13 stack.pop() != bracketPair[kStart]: 14 return False 15 16 if len(stack) == 0: 17 return True 18 19 return False </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	82	Balanced-LS_-x	Lombard	Same	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 def ANON(s): 2 b = [('(',')'), ('[',']'), ('{','}')] 3 ks = 0 4 ke = 1 5 st = [] 6 7 for c in s: 8 for bp in b: 9 if c == bp[ks]: 10 st.append(c) 11 elif c == bp[ke]: 12 if len(st) == 0 or \ 13 st.pop() != bp[ks]: 14 return False 15 16 if len(st) == 0: 17 return True 18 19 return False </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	83	Balanced-L_C-x	Beale	Same	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String s) { 2 HashMap<Character, Character> bm 3 = new HashMap<Character, Character>(); 4 bm.put('{', '}'); 5 bm.put('[', ']'); 6 bm.put('(', ')'); 7 Stack<Character> bs = new Stack<Character>(); 8 9 for (char c : s.toCharArray()) { 10 if (!bs.isEmpty() && 11 bm.get(bs.peek()) == c) { 12 bs.pop(); 13 } else if (bm.containsKey(c)) { 14 bs.push(c); 15 } else { 16 return false; 17 } 18 } 19 return bs.isEmpty(); 20 } 21 22 23 24 </pre> <pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String e) { 2 if ((e.length() % 2) == 1) return false; 3 else { 4 Stack<Character> s = new Stack<>(); 5 for (char b : e.toCharArray()) 6 switch (b) { 7 case '{': 8 s.push('{'); 9 break; 10 case '(': 11 s.push('('); 12 break; 13 case '[': 14 s.push('['); 15 break; 16 default: 17 if (s.isEmpty() b != s.peek()) { 18 return false; 19 } 20 s.pop(); 21 } 22 return s.isEmpty(); 23 } 24 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	35	Balanced-L_C-N	Beale	Same	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean isBalanced(String s) { 2 HashMap<Character, Character> bracketMap 3 = new HashMap<Character, Character>(); 4 bracketMap.put('{', '}'); 5 bracketMap.put('[', ']'); 6 bracketMap.put('(', ')'); 7 Stack<Character> bracketStack = 8 new Stack<Character>(); 9 10 for (char c: s.toCharArray()) { 11 if (!bracketStack.isEmpty() && 12 bracketMap.get(bracketStack.peek()) == c) { 13 bracketStack.pop(); 14 } else if (bracketMap.containsKey(c)) { 15 bracketStack.push(c); 16 } else { 17 return false; 18 } 19 } 20 return bracketStack.isEmpty(); 21 } 22 23 24 </pre> <pre> 1 public static boolean isBalanced(String expression) { 2 if ((expression.length() % 2) == 1) return false; 3 else { 4 Stack<Character> s = new Stack<>(); 5 for (char bracket : expression.toCharArray()) 6 switch (bracket) { 7 case '{': 8 s.push('{'); 9 break; 10 case '(': 11 s.push('('); 12 break; 13 case '[': 14 s.push('['); 15 break; 16 default: 17 if (s.isEmpty() bracket != s.peek()) { 18 return false; 19 } 20 s.pop(); 21 } 22 return s.isEmpty(); 23 } 24 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	36	Balanced-L__-N	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 def isBalanced(strInput): 2 brackets = [('(',')'), ('[',']'), ('{','}')] 3 kStart = 0 4 kEnd = 1 5 stack = [] 6 7 for char in strInput: 8 for bracketPair in brackets: 9 if char == bracketPair[kStart]: 10 stack.append(char) 11 elif char == bracketPair[kEnd]: 12 if len(stack) == 0 or \ 13 stack.pop() != bracketPair[kStart]: 14 return False 15 16 if len(stack) == 0: 17 return True 18 19 return False </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	84	Balanced-L__x	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 def ANON(s): 2 b = [('(', ')'), ('[', ']'), ('{', '}')] 3 ks = 0 4 ke = 1 5 st = [] 6 7 for c in s: 8 for bp in b: 9 if c == bp[ks]: 10 st.append(c) 11 elif c == bp[ke]: 12 if len(st) == 0 or \ 13 st.pop() != bp[ks]: 14 return False 15 16 if len(st) == 0: 17 return True 18 19 return False </pre>
									<pre> 1 def ANON(p): 2 m = 0 3 for c in p: 4 if c in '({[': 5 m += 1 6 elif c in "]})": 7 m -= 1 8 if m < 0: 9 return False 10 return m == 0 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	85	Balanced-SC-x	Wall	Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String b) { 2 Map<Character, Character> br = 3 new HashMap<>(); 4 br.put('(', ')'); 5 br.put('[', ']'); 6 br.put('{', '}'); 7 if (b.length() % 2 != 0) { 8 return false; 9 } 10 11 Stack<Character> h = new Stack(); 12 for (char ch : b.toCharArray()) { 13 if (br.containsKey(ch)) { 14 h.push(br.get(ch)); 15 } else if (h.isEmpty() 16 ch != h.pop()) { 17 return false; 18 } 19 } 20 return h.isEmpty(); 21 } </pre>
									<pre> 1 def ANON(s): 2 b = { 3 '(': ')', 4 '{': '}', 5 '[': ']' 6 } 7 st = [] 8 for c in s: 9 l = 0 10 if st: 11 l = st[len(st) - 1] 12 if st and l in b \ 13 and b[l] == c: 14 st.pop() 15 else: 16 st.append(c) 17 18 return not st 19 20 21 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	37	Balanced-SC-N	Wall	Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean isBalanced(String brackets) { 2 Map<Character, Character> braces = 3 new HashMap<>(); 4 braces.put('(', ')'); 5 braces.put('[', ']'); 6 braces.put('{', '}'); 7 if (brackets.length() % 2 != 0) { 8 return false; 9 } 10 11 Stack<Character> halfBraces = new Stack(); 12 for (char ch : brackets.toCharArray()) { 13 if (braces.containsKey(ch)) { 14 halfBraces.push(braces.get(ch)); 15 } else if (halfBraces.isEmpty() 16 ch != halfBraces.pop()) { 17 return false; 18 } 19 } 20 return halfBraces.isEmpty(); 21 } </pre> <pre> 1 def balancedBrackets(string): 2 brackets = { 3 '(': ')', 4 '{': '}', 5 '[': ']' 6 } 7 stack = [] 8 for char in string: 9 last = 0 10 if stack: 11 last = stack[len(stack) - 1] 12 if stack and last in brackets \ 13 and brackets[last] == char: 14 stack.pop() 15 else: 16 stack.append(char) 17 18 return not stack </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	86	Balanced-_S_-x	Mulholland	Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String s) { 2 HashMap<Character, Character> bm 3 = new HashMap<Character, Character>(); 4 bm.put('{', '}'); 5 bm.put('[', ']'); 6 bm.put('(', ')'); 7 Stack<Character> bs = new Stack<Character>(); 8 9 for (char c: s.toCharArray()) { 10 if (!bs.isEmpty() && 11 bm.get(bs.peek()) == c) { 12 bs.pop(); 13 } else if (bm.containsKey(c)) { 14 bs.push(c); 15 } else { 16 return false; 17 } 18 } 19 return bs.isEmpty(); 20 } </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(s): 2 b = [('(',')'), ('[',']'), ('{','}')] 3 stk = [] 4 5 for c in s: 6 for st, e in b: 7 if c == st: 8 stk.append(c) 9 elif c == e: 10 if len(stk) == 0 or \ 11 stk.pop() != st: 12 return False 13 14 return True </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	38	Balanced-_S_-N	Mulholland	Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static boolean isBalanced(String s) { 2 HashMap<Character, Character> bracketMap 3 = new HashMap<Character, Character>(); 4 bracketMap.put('{', '}'); 5 bracketMap.put('[', ']'); 6 bracketMap.put('(', ')'); 7 Stack<Character> bracketStack = 8 new Stack<Character>(); 9 10 for (char c: s.toCharArray()) { 11 if (!bracketStack.isEmpty() && 12 bracketMap.get(bracketStack.peek()) == c) { 13 bracketStack.pop(); 14 } else if (bracketMap.containsKey(c)) { 15 bracketStack.push(c); 16 } else { 17 return false; 18 } 19 } 20 return bracketStack.isEmpty(); 21 } </pre> <pre> 1 def isBalanced(strInput): 2 brackets = [('(',')'), ('[',']'), ('{','}')] 3 stack = [] 4 5 for char in strInput: 6 for start, end in brackets: 7 if char == start: 8 stack.append(char) 9 elif char == end: 10 if len(stack) == 0 or \ 11 stack.pop() != start: 12 return False 13 14 return True 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	87	Balanced-__C-x	Sunset	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static boolean ANON(String e) { 2 if ((e.length() % 2) == 1) return false; 3 else { 4 Stack<Character> s = new Stack<>(); 5 for (char b : e.toCharArray()) 6 switch (b) { 7 case '{': 8 s.push('}'); 9 break; 10 case '(': 11 s.push(')'); 12 break; 13 case '[': 14 s.push(']'); 15 break; 16 default: 17 if (s.isEmpty() b != s.peek()) { 18 return false; 19 } 20 s.pop(); 21 } 22 return s.isEmpty(); 23 } 24 } </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(s): 2 b = [('(',')'), ('[',']'), ('{','}')] 3 ks = 0 4 ke = 1 5 st = [] 6 7 for c in s: 8 for bp in b: 9 if c == bp[ks]: 10 st.append(c) 11 elif c == bp[ke]: 12 if len(st) == 0 or \ 13 st.pop() != bp[ks]: 14 return False 15 16 if len(st) == 0: 17 return True 18 19 return False </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
5	39	Balanced-__C-N	Sunset	Different	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE

```

1 public static boolean isBalanced(String expression) {
2     if ((expression.length() % 2) == 1) return false;
3     else {
4         Stack<Character> s = new Stack<>();
5         for (char bracket : expression.toCharArray())
6             switch (bracket) {
7                 case '{':
8                     s.push('{');
9                     break;
10                case '(':
11                    s.push('(');
12                    break;
13                case '[':
14                    s.push('[');
15                    break;
16                default:
17                    if (s.isEmpty() || bracket != s.peek()) {
18                        return false;
19                    }
20                    s.pop();
21                }
22            return s.isEmpty();
23        }
24    }

```

```

1 def isBalanced(strInput):
2     brackets = [ ('(', ')'), ('[', ']'), ('{', '}')]
3     kStart = 0
4     kEnd = 1
5     stack = []
6
7     for char in strInput:
8         for bracketPair in brackets:
9             if char == bracketPair[kStart]:
10                stack.append(char)
11            elif char == bracketPair[kEnd]:
12                if len(stack) == 0 or \
13                   stack.pop() != bracketPair[kStart]:
14                    return False
15
16        if len(stack) == 0:
17            return True
18
19        return False
20
21
22
23
24

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
5	88	Balanced-__-x	Bourbon	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE

```

1 public static boolean ANON(String s) {
2     int b = 0;
3     for(int i = 0; i < s.length(); i++) {
4         char c = s.charAt(i);
5         if (c == '(' || c == '[' || c == '{') {
6             b++;
7         }
8         else if (c == ')' || c == ']' || c == '}') {
9             b--;
10        }
11        if (b == -1) {
12            return false;
13        }
14    }
15    return b == 0;
16 }
17
18
1 def ANON(s):
2     b = {
3         '(': ')',
4         '{': '}',
5         '[': ']'
6     }
7     st = []
8     for c in s:
9         l = 0
10        if st:
11            l = st[len(st) - 1]
12            if st and l in b \
13                and b[l] == c:
14                st.pop()
15            else:
16                st.append(c)
17
18    return not st

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
5	40	Balanced-___-N	Bourbon	Diferent	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static boolean bracketsBalanced(String s) { 2 int bracketLevel = 0; 3 for(int i = 0; i < s.length(); i++) { 4 char c = s.charAt(i); 5 if (c == '(' c == '[' c == '{') { 6 bracketLevel++; 7 } 8 else if (c == ')' c == ']' c == '}') { 9 bracketLevel--; 10 } 11 if (bracketLevel == -1) { 12 return false; 13 } 14 } 15 return bracketLevel == 0; 16 } 17 18 1 def balancedBrackets(string): 2 brackets = { 3 '(': ')', 4 '{': '}', 5 '[': ']' 6 } 7 stack = [] 8 for char in string: 9 last = 0 10 if stack: 11 last = stack[len(stack) - 1] 12 if stack and last in brackets \ 13 and brackets[last] == char: 14 stack.pop() 15 else: 16 stack.append(char) 17 18 return not stack </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
9	41	RemoveDuplicates-LS Canton		Same	Different	TRUE	Meaningful	TRUE

```

1 public static String removeDuplicates (String s) {
2     if (s.isEmpty())
3         return "";
4
5     StringBuilder resultBuilder = new StringBuilder();
6     char previous = s.charAt (0);
7     resultBuilder.append (previous);
8     for (int i = 1; i < s.length(); i++) {
9         char current = s.charAt (i);
10        if (previous != current) {
11            resultBuilder.append (current);
12            previous = current;
13        }
14    }
15    return resultBuilder.toString ();
16 }

```

```

1 public static String removeDuplicates(String orig)
2 {
3     if (orig.length() == 0) return "";
4     String result = "" + orig.charAt(0);
5     for (int i = 1; i < orig.length(); i++)
6         if (orig.charAt(i-1) != orig.charAt(i))
7             result+=orig.charAt(i);
8     return result;
9 }

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	89	RemoveDuplicates-LS Canton		Same	Different	TRUE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String s) { 2 if (s.isEmpty()) 3 return ""; 4 5 StringBuilder rb = new StringBuilder(); 6 char p = s.charAt (0); 7 rb.append (p); 8 for (int i = 1; i < s.length(); i ++) { 9 char current = s.charAt (i); 10 if (p != current) { 11 rb.append (current); 12 p = current; 13 } 14 } 15 return rb.toString (); 16 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	90	RemoveDuplicates-LS	Lombard	Same	Different	TRUE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 def ANON(S): 2 res = list() 3 for c in S: 4 if res and res[-1] == c: 5 pass 6 else: 7 res.append(c) 8 return "".join(res) </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(st): 2 st = list(st) 3 i = 1 4 while i < len(st): 5 if st[i] == st[i - 1]: 6 st.pop(i) 7 i += 1 8 return "".join(st) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	42	RemoveDuplicates-LS Lombard		Same	Different	TRUE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 def removeAdjacentDuplicates(S): 2 res = list() 3 for c in S: 4 if res and res[-1] == c: 5 pass 6 else: 7 res.append(c) 8 return "".join(res) </pre> <pre> 1 def removeAdjacentRepeats(st): 2 st = list(st) 3 i = 1 4 while i < len(st): 5 if st[i] == st[i - 1]: 6 st.pop(i) 7 i += 1 8 return "".join(st) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	43	RemoveDuplicates-L	Beale	Same	Same	TRUE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 def removeadjacent(orig): 2 if len(orig) == 0: return orig 3 res = "" 4 for i in range(1, len(orig)): 5 if orig[i-1] != orig[i]: 6 res += orig[i] 7 return orig[0] + res </pre> <pre> 1 def removeAdjacentDuplicates(l): 2 return "".join([l[i] for i in range(len(l)-1) 3 if l[i]!=l[i+1]] + [l[-1:]]) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	91	RemoveDuplicates-L	Beale	Same	Same	TRUE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 def ANON(orig): 2 if len(orig) == 0: return orig 3 res = "" 4 for i in range(1, len(orig)): 5 if orig[i-1] != orig[i]: 6 res += orig[i] 7 return orig[0] + res </pre> <pre> 1 v def ANON(l): 2 v return "".join([l[i] for i in range(len(l)-1) 3 if l[i]!=l[i+1]] + [l[-1:]]) 4 5 6 7 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	44	RemoveDuplicates-L	Broadway	Same	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String removeDuplicates(String orig) 2 { 3 if (orig.length() == 0) return ""; 4 String result = "" + orig.charAt(0); 5 for (int i = 1; i < orig.length(); i++) 6 if (orig.charAt(i-1) != orig.charAt(i)) 7 result+=orig.charAt(i); 8 return result; 9 } 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 </pre> <pre> 1 public static String removeDuplicates(String str){ 2 Stack<Character> st=new Stack<>(); 3 StringBuilder sb=new StringBuilder(); 4 for (int i=0;i<str.length();i++){ 5 if(!st.isEmpty() && 6 st.peek()==str.charAt(i)) { 7 st.pop(); 8 }else{ 9 st.push(str.charAt(i)); 10 } 11 } 12 13 for (Character ch:st){ 14 sb.append(ch); 15 } 16 return sb.toString(); 17 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	92	RemoveDuplicates-L_Broadway		Same	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String o) { 2 if (o.length() == 0) return ""; 3 String r = "" + o.charAt(0); 4 for (int i = 1; i < o.length(); i++) 5 if (o.charAt(i-1) != o.charAt(i)) 6 r+=o.charAt(i); 7 return r; 8 } 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 </pre> <pre> 1 public static String ANON(String str){ 2 Stack<Character> st=new Stack<>(); 3 StringBuilder sb=new StringBuilder(); 4 for (int i=0;i<str.length();i++){ 5 if(!st.isEmpty() && 6 st.peek()==str.charAt(i)) { 7 st.pop(); 8 }else{ 9 st.push(str.charAt(i)); 10 } 11 } 12 13 for (Character ch:st){ 14 sb.append(ch); 15 } 16 return sb.toString(); 17 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	45	RemoveDuplicates-_S Wall		Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String removeDuplicates(String orig) 2 { 3 if (orig.length() == 0) return ""; 4 String result = "" + orig.charAt(0); 5 for (int i = 1; i < orig.length(); i++) 6 if (orig.charAt(i-1) != orig.charAt(i)) 7 result+=orig.charAt(i); 8 return result; 9 } </pre> <pre> 1 def removeadjacent(orig): 2 if len(orig) == 0: return orig 3 res = "" 4 for i in range(1, len(orig)): 5 if orig[i-1] != orig[i]: 6 res += orig[i] 7 return orig[0] + res 8 9 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	93	RemoveDuplicates-_S Wall		Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String o) { 2 if (o.length() == 0) return ""; 3 String r = "" + o.charAt(0); 4 for (int i = 1; i < o.length(); i++) 5 if (o.charAt(i-1) != o.charAt(i)) 6 r+=o.charAt(i); 7 return r; 8 } </pre> <pre> 1 def ANON(orig): 2 if len(orig) == 0: return orig 3 res = "" 4 for i in range(1, len(orig)): 5 if orig[i-1] != orig[i]: 6 res += orig[i] 7 return orig[0] + res 8 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	46	RemoveDuplicates-_S Mulholland		Different	Same	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String removeDuplicates(String str){ 2 Stack<Character> st=new Stack<>(); 3 StringBuilder sb=new StringBuilder(); 4 for (int i=0;i<str.length();i++){ 5 if(!st.isEmpty() && 6 st.peek()==str.charAt(i)) { 7 st.pop(); 8 }else{ 9 st.push(str.charAt(i)); 10 } 11 } 12 13 for (Character ch:st){ 14 sb.append(ch); 15 } 16 return sb.toString(); 17 } </pre> <pre> 1 def removeAdjacentDuplicates(S): 2 res = list() 3 for c in S: 4 if res and res[-1] == c: 5 pass 6 else: 7 res.append(c) 8 return "".join(res) 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones
9	94	RemoveDuplicates-_S	Mulholland	Different	Same	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE

```

1 public static String ANON(String str){
2     Stack<Character> st=new Stack<>();
3     StringBuilder sb=new StringBuilder();
4     for (int i=0;i<str.length();i++){
5         if(!st.isEmpty() &&
6             st.peek()==str.charAt(i)) {
7             st.pop();
8         }else{
9             st.push(str.charAt(i));
10        }
11    }
12
13    for (Character ch:st){
14        sb.append(ch);
15    }
16    return sb.toString();
17 }

```

```

1 def ANON(S):
2     res = list()
3     for c in S:
4         if res and res[-1] == c:
5             pass
6         else:
7             res.append(c)
8     return "".join(res)
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	47	RemoveDuplicates-__Sunset		Different	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String removeDuplicates (String s) { 2 if (s.isEmpty()) 3 return ""; 4 5 StringBuilder resultBuilder = new StringBuilder(); 6 char previous = s.charAt (0); 7 resultBuilder.append (previous); 8 for (int i = 1; i < s.length(); i++) { 9 char current = s.charAt (i); 10 if (previous != current) { 11 resultBuilder.append (current); 12 previous = current; 13 } 14 } 15 return resultBuilder.toString (); 16 } </pre> <pre> 1 def removeAdjacentDuplicates(l): 2 return "".join([l[i] for i in range(len(l)-1) 3 if l[i]!=l[i+1]] + [l[-1:]]) </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	95	RemoveDuplicates-__	Sunset	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	TRUE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String s) { 2 if (s.isEmpty()) 3 return ""; 4 5 StringBuilder rb = new StringBuilder(); 6 char p = s.charAt (0); 7 rb.append (p); 8 for (int i = 1; i < s.length(); i ++) { 9 char current = s.charAt (i); 10 if (p != current) { 11 rb.append (current); 12 p = current; 13 } 14 } 15 return rb.toString (); 16 } </pre>

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	96	RemoveDuplicates-__	Bourbon	Different	Different	FALSE	Obfuscated	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String ANON(String s) { 2 if (s.isEmpty()) 3 return ""; 4 5 StringBuilder rb = new StringBuilder(); 6 char p = s.charAt (0); 7 rb.append (p); 8 for (int i = 1; i < s.length(); i ++) { 9 char current = s.charAt (i); 10 if (p != current) { 11 rb.append (current); 12 p = current; 13 } 14 } 15 return rb.toString (); 16 } </pre>

```

1 def ANON(st):
2     st = list(st)
3     i = 1
4     while i < len(st):
5         if st[i] == st[i - 1]:
6             st.pop(i)
7             i += 1
8     return "".join(st)

```

Task Class	Index	Full Name	Nickname	Language	Structure	Revised from Original Structure	Names	Clones	
9	48	RemoveDuplicates-__	Bourbon	Different	Different	FALSE	Meaningful	FALSE	<pre> 1 public static String removeDuplicates (String s) { 2 if (s.isEmpty()) 3 return ""; 4 5 StringBuilder resultBuilder = new StringBuilder(); 6 char previous = s.charAt (0); 7 resultBuilder.append (previous); 8 for (int i = 1; i < s.length(); i ++) { 9 char current = s.charAt (i); 10 if (previous != current) { 11 resultBuilder.append (current); 12 previous = current; 13 } 14 } 15 return resultBuilder.toString (); 16 } </pre> <pre> 1 def removeAdjacentRepeats(st): 2 st = list(st) 3 i = 1 4 while i < len(st): 5 if st[i] == st[i - 1]: 6 st.pop(i) 7 i += 1 8 return "".join(st) </pre>